

Availability of Pores of Silica Gel to the Metal Complexes of Anils

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Exclusion of ions from the pore of the adsorbent results in the decrease in the factor A, pore availability. This phenomenon occurs when the solvent is preferentially adsorbed or the solute interacts with the surface of the adsorbent. A few study of water soluble complexes of cobalt with hydrophobic and hydrophilic ligands have thrown some light on this view point.

The behaviour in non-aqueous solvent, acetone, with Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) complexes of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino anil of β -naphthyl glyoxal as adsorbates was studied using silica gel of known porosity.

The values of A were always found to be greater than 100. The following order of pore availability was observed :—

A comparison of the ionic radii (assuming that the solute does not extend its ionic radii in non-aqueous medium) has shown that the pore availability increases with decrease in the size of the ion.

Experiments performed in slightly acidic medium give higher values of A. It may be attributed to the dissociation of the complex.

Silica gel possesses enough pores which can act as centres for the adsorption of ions or solvents or both. With pure solvent it may be a purely physical phenomenon but when solutions are used then the mechanism of adsorption is quite complicated and several factors have to be taken into account to explain it.

The exclusion of aqueous ions from part of the pore volume of a small pore silica gel has been the subject of several studies.¹⁻³ The exclusion effect has been related to the relative sizes of the ion hydrates, where the "hydrate" may include water molecules ordered by the ion beyond the first shell. In the present paper we report results for the Zn⁺⁺, Cd⁺⁺ and Hg⁺⁺ complexes of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino anil of β -naphthyl glyoxal on silica gel employing the polar compound acetone as the solvent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : Stock solutions of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration of Zn⁺⁺, Cd⁺⁺, Hg⁺⁺ complexes of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino anil of β -naphthyl glyoxal⁴ were prepared in double distilled acetone. Silica gel was prepared as

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described in our publication⁵. The pore volume and surface area of the gel were 0.50 ml/g and 700 m²/g, respectively.

Procedure : At 25°, 25 ml. (brownish yellow coloured complex) solutions of different concentrations (5.0; 3.33; 2.50; 2.0; 1.66; 1.42; 1.25; 1.11 and $1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$.) were mixed with (12.0 g) silica gel in a number of glass stoppered bottles. The mixtures were shaken for about 4 hr. in a const. temp. bath and kept overnight to attain the equilibrium. The contents of the bottles were then centrifuged for about 5 minutes and the concentration of the centrifugate was estimated from absorbance measurements (carried out at λ max. 540-580 m μ) using Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer.

Some solutions were acidified with hydrochloric acid ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) in order to repress the possible cationic exchange with hydrogen of the surface silanol groups.

Formula used : "Percent availability", A , is the percentage of the pore volume of the gel available to a solute, using as 100% reference the pore volume available to the solvent. Thus, when A is less than 100% the solute does not see as much pore volume as the solvent. To measure A , a solution of known volume and concentration is mixed with a known weight of gel and the mixture is held at the desired temperature (25°). After a steady state is achieved, the concentration of the solution external to the gel particle is measured. The amount of solute (in moles) within the pores of 1 g. of gel is

$$\frac{C_i V - C_f (V - WP)}{W}$$

where C_i and V are the concentration (moles/ml.) and volume (ml.) of the solution added to W g. gel of pore volume P ml/g. and C_f is the concentration of the solution external to the gel particles when a steady state is achieved. The amount of solute (in moles) there would be in the pores of 1 g. of gel if the per cent availability were 100% is $C_f P$. Therefore, A is given by dividing the actual amount of $C_f P$ and multiplying by 100.

$$A = \frac{C_i - C_f (V - WP)}{W} \times \frac{1}{C_f P} \times 100$$

$$A = \left[\frac{V}{WP} - \left(\frac{C_i}{C_f} - 1 \right) + 1 \right] \times 100$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The average A values with and without added hydrochloric acid for Zn⁺⁺, Cd⁺⁺ and Hg⁺⁺ are the same. It is concluded that the cation exchange is not a complicating factor. The pore availability values A , for all the three complexes are higher than hundred (Table 1). Values smaller than hundred can be obtained under two conditions : (i) the silica pores would exclude the complex cation in preference to the solvent, (ii) the cation increases in size through solvation.

Higher values of A rule out either of the two possibilities. Since adsorption is intimately connected with pore availability (greater the pore availability, larger the adsorption of the solute), it may be safely concluded that the silica gel does not make its pore available to the solvent for adsorption. This is quite a normal behaviour, because unlike water, acetone will exhibit very little tendency to interact with the polar silica gel.

TABLE I
Availabilities for Zn⁺⁺, Cd⁺⁺ and Hg⁺⁺ Complexes

Cation ^a	A% ^b No added acid	A% ^b 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M HCl
C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ OZnCl ₂	145.91(8)	158.39(8)
C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O.CdCl ₂	124.74(8)	134.45(8)
C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O.HgCl ₂	115.57(7)	129.09(7)
C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O.ZnCl ₂	164.15(5)	176.11(5)
C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O.CdCl ₂	152.60(5)	162.08(5)
C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O.HgCl ₂	132.97(6)	139.55(6)

^a All compounds are chlorides.

^b Parenthetical number is number of experiments in indicated concentration range. Average error in A is $\pm 3\%$.

The large availability of silica pores to the cations go to show that the complex ion does not become large through solvation. It appears that the ligands *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino anil of β -naphthyl glyoxal are lyophobic in character and hence there is little tendency of the solvent either to solvate itself or diffuse into the coordinating core to make the complex ion large enough for exclusion from the silica pores.

Further confirmation to the fact that ion size largely influences the pore availability (and consequently adsorption) is forthcoming on comparing the average A values with the ionic radii of the cations. Assuming that the simple metal ions and the complex ion does not differ very much in size due to nonsolvation or hydration if the medium is aqueous, the comparative values would be.

TABLE II

Cation	Ionic Radii	Pore availability 'A'	
		(<i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal complexes)	(<i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil of β -naphthyl glyoxal complexes)
Zn ⁺⁺	0.74Å	145.91	164.15
Cd ⁺⁺	0.97Å	124.74	152.60
Hg ⁺⁺	1.10Å	115.57	132.97

From the above table it is quite evident that the pore availability increases with decrease in the size of the ion. The contention that pore availability is closely related to

adsorption is borne out by the fact that the plots between 'A' and the initial concentration of the complex give curves similar to adsorption isotherm curves (vide typical curves) (Figs 1-2).

Addition of acid to the adsorbate would normally bring about a decrease in the value of A due to exchange adsorption of hydrogen ions on silica gel. But here the values become higher on addition of even $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ HCl. This would only be possible if the complex is unstable in presence of acid, decomposing either into simple metal ions or changing into a species which, will readily react with the silica gel.

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